

Human Origins - Digital Future

July 27 - 31, 2020

Program and Abstracts

Convener

Research Centre ROCEEH -
„The Role of Culture in Early Expansions of Humans“
Heidelberg Academy of Sciences and Humanities
Senckenberg Research Institute Frankfurt/Main
Eberhard Karls University of Tübingen

**HEIDELBERGER AKADEMIE
DER WISSENSCHAFTEN**
Akademie der Wissenschaften
des Landes Baden-Württemberg

**THE ROLE
OF CULTURE
IN EARLY
EXPANSIONS
OF HUMANS**

SENCKENBERG
conference

EBERHARD KARLS
UNIVERSITÄT
TÜBINGEN

General Program

Monday, July 27, 2020	14:00-16:00 CEST Databases
Tuesday, July 28, 2020	14:00-16:00 CEST Methods
Wednesday, July 29, 2020	14:00-16:00 CEST Applications
Thursday, July 30, 2020	14:00-16:00 CEST Products
Friday, July 31, 2020	14:00-16:00 CEST Perspectives Closing Discussion

Monday, July 27, 2020

14:00 CEST Miriam N. Haidle
Welcome

DATABASES, Chair Volker Hochschild

14:15 CEST Eric Grimm, John W. Williams
The Neotoma Paleoecology Database: Shared Standards, Community Curation, and Active Reanalysis of Paleo Data

14:30 CEST Andrew W. Kandel, ROCEEH Team
A Beginner's Guide to the ROCEEH Out of Africa Database

14:45 CEST Franco Niccolucci
A data-centric archaeological research methodology: opportunities and risks

15:00 CEST Christopher Nicholson
Challenges of Archiving Complex Archaeological Datasets for Reuse: An Example from the American Southwest

15:15 CEST Jesús Rodríguez
The specific problems of palaeontological databases and how NQMDB deals with them.

15:30 CEST Discussion

Tuesday, July 28, 2020

METHODS, Chair Ericson Hölzchen & Christian Sommer

- 14:00 CEST Miriam N. Haidle
Summing up Day 1
- 14:15 CEST Juan Antonio Barcelo
Solving archaeological inverse problems. A reverse engineering approach
- 14:30 CEST Christian Sommer, Adel Omran, Volker Hochschild, ROCEEH Team
New perspectives for data exploration in ROAD
- 14.45 CEST Ingo Timm
Artificial Intelligence and Paleoanthropological Databases
- 15:00 CEST Alice J. Williams
How well does the Circumscription Theory Explain the Formation of Complex Societies? Using Agent-based Models to Evaluate Archaeological Theories against Existing Archaeological Data
- 15:15 CEST Christian Willmes
PaleoMaps: Creating, Collecting and Compiling Geospatial Paleoenvironment Data for Culture Eenvironment-Interaction Modeling Applications
- 15:30 CEST Discussion

Wednesday, July 29, 2020

APPLICATIONS, Chair Andrew W. Kandel

14:00 CEST Miriam N. Haidle
Summing up Day 2

14:15 – 15:30 CEST

Rimtautas Dapschauskas, Matthias Göden, Christian Sommer, Andrew W. Kandel

Using a Geo-relational Spatial Information System to Examine Questions about the Large scale Development of Cultural Behavior in Human Evolution: The Example of Ochre in the African Middle Stone Age

Ewa Dutkiewicz

Structuring the Unstructured: Databases for Paleolithic Art

Christine Hertler

The ROAD Map Module

Ericson Hölzchen, Christian Sommer, Christine Hertler

NeMo – An agent-based model for simulating Neanderthal mobility

Zara Kanaeva, ROCEEH Team

ROAD Summary Data Sheet: A publication and data sharing tool

Ana Mateos, Christian Willmes, Jesús Rodríguez

Matching datasets and palaeoenvironment to frame Human Palaeoecology in Europe around MIS 11

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Is a decentralized, non-standardized approach to data sharing in archaeology good enough?

Mika Puspaningrum, Christine Hertler, Angela Bruch, Iwan P. Anwar, Ericson Hölzchen, Susanne Krüger, Agus T. Hascaryo, Jan-Olaf Reschke

Living in Sangiran

Denné Reed

Paleo Core: A platform for data integration in paleoanthropology

Manuel Will, Mario Krapp, Jay T. Stock, Andrea Manica
*Combining Paleoenvironmental and Paleoanthropological Datasets to
Understand Human Brain and Body Size Evolution*

Andreas Zimmermann, Isabell Schmidt
Prehistoric Population Dynamics — extended

15:30 CEST Discussion

Thursday, July 30, 2020

PRODUCTS, Chair Christine Hertler

- 14:00 CEST Miriam N. Haidle
Summing up Day 3
- 14:15 CEST Yasuhisa Kondo
Interdisciplinary challenges of the Cultural History of PaleoAsia project and its database development: Lessons learnt
- 14:30 CEST Wolfgang Börner
Wien Kulturgut: Web Portal for the Contribution of Archaeological Data from the Palaeolithic until Today
- 14:45 CEST Liane Giemsch, Tanja Neumann
METAhub Frankfurt – A Database as Link Between Museum Cultures and Performative Art
- 15:00 CEST Matthias Lang, Philippe Kluge, Colin Emonds, Vinzenz Rosenkranz
Spacialist – A Virtual Research Environment for the Spatial Humanities
- 15:15 CEST Simon Goring
Connecting Disciplinary Data and Resources: Using the Throughput Database to Speed Up Discovery
- 15:30 CEST Discussion

Friday, July 31, 2020

PERSPECTIVES, Chair Volker Hochschild

- 14:00 CEST Miriam N. Haidle
Summing up Day 4
- 14:15 CEST Sarah Kansa
Interview
- 14:45 CEST Peter McKeague
Interview
- 15:00 CEST Julian Richards
Interview
- 15:15 CEST Dieta Svoboda-Baas
Interview
- 15:30 CEST Discussion and Summary

Abstracts
in alphabetical order

Solving archaeological inverse problems. A reverse engineering approach

Juan A. Barceló

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“Reverse engineering” has been defined as the study of a sample of a product, device or machine, to discover how it functions or was made. The goal is to find the functional principles that make it work. It may be simply measuring all the parts and analysing the materials, to be able to reproduce it. The underlying idea seems to be if you learn how to make it, you know how it works. That means that if you can reconstruct the process by which the object was created, you will understand why it has that specific shape, and size, why it is made of this material, why its surface has those visual or tactile properties, etc.

Archaeology is a form of reverse engineering for the social sciences. It seems the best way to approach the classical archaeological problem, formally: reconstructing the cause –social action- based on an observation of the effects –the archaeological record.

In most current applications of the reverse engineering approach in archaeology, it seems reduced to digitalization: how to reconstruct the original surface based on a sample of 3D points acquired through photogrammetry or laser scans. However, as the very idea of reverse bioengineering brings about, reverse engineering is not restricted to digital imaging or shape analysis. In biological systems, reverse engineering has been invoked to understand how living beings have evolved, that is, the task of inferring adaptive function from structure”. In this paper I consider this approach in functional analysis of different kinds of archaeological items, from buildings to bones, from pottery and instruments to territories. It presents different ways to express mathematically human behavior, making emphasis on inverse kinematics methods and different variations of the finite analysis method.

Wien Kulturgut: Web Portal for the Contribution of Archaeological Data from the Palaeolithic until Today

Wolfgang Börner

Urban Archaeology of Vienna, Obere Augartenstraße 26-28, 1020 Vienna, Austria

When have the first human beings appeared in the Vienna Basin?

The city of Vienna has been closely connected with relics of the Ice Age for several centuries. In the year 1546 bones of a mammoth were interpreted as bones of Gog and Magog, the biblical giants. Those were found during the construction of the north tower of St. Stephen's Cathedral in 1443 and labelled with AEIOU ("*Austriae est imperare orbi universe*" or "*Austria erit in orbe ultima*") - the motto of Emperor Friedrich III.

There is a reason to believe that the territory of Vienna was also an important region for the Ice Age hunting and gathering societies as the surrounding area of Lower Austria and the Danube region. It can be assumed that the geographically prominent situation like the "Wiener Pforte" represented a typical "landmark" for the Ice Age groups.

Twenty years ago, in December 2000 the Web Portal "Wien Kulturgut" (former "Wiener Kulturgüterkataster") has gone online. Since this time much has changed in technological aspects and new content was uploaded. Since the start it was highly accepted by the citizens of Vienna and also by tourists.

Vienna's cultural heritage Web Portal- the digital cultural city map of the city of Vienna - provides access to essential characteristics of the city's identity: Many maps show the cultural-historical and the development of urban planning from the beginning to the present.

The web portal offers everyone who is interested access to digitally recorded cultural heritage, which is stored and researched at various locations in Vienna. More than 4000 digitally available archaeological resources can be searched and filtered specifically according to different criteria.

In my talk I will present the Web Portal as analysis tool together with the Vienna Archaeological Geographic Information System (VAGIS).

Using a Geo-relational Spatial Information System to Examine Questions about the Large scale Development of Cultural Behavior in Human Evolution: The Example of Ochre in the African Middle Stone Age

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Archaeological databases should not be an end in themselves. Rather, they provide tools for addressing research questions based on large volumes of data that cannot be examined using conventional methods. In particular, large-scale archaeological meta-analyses about the long term development of cultural behavior during the Pleistocene are best approached with geo-relational spatial information systems such as the ROCEEH Out of Africa Database (ROAD). In our poster presentation we report the results of a project about ochre use during the African Middle Stone Age. We assessed data from 100 different archaeological sites and entered them into ROAD. The published data from each locality was evaluated based on the character and quality of the ochre artifacts reported, the nature of the excavation, the stratigraphy of the site, and the reliability of its dating. To overcome problems associated with variable data inherent in our age model, we employed the statistical concept of *time averaging* by developing an analytical tool called “time slice”. This tool tallies the numbers of localities and assemblages which meet certain criteria as specified in a predefined query. It also allows the user to slide the analytical window across the scope of analysis at a given time interval. We wrote two queries for this analysis, one that generated a list of African localities containing assemblages of ochre, and another for stone artifacts. This method enabled us to identify three distinct chronological phases of ochre use between 500,000 and 40,000 years ago. However, with regard to statements about the evolution of cultural behavior, data mining can only be the first step. In the next step, the results must be subjected to an interpretation process that is not based on the data themselves. For this purpose we integrated our results with findings about ritualized behavior from primatology, the cognitive sciences, and anthropology. This allowed us to offer some well-founded conclusions about the evolution of ritual behavior during a critical phase as *Homo sapiens* developed into a socially complex bio-cultural species, not fundamentally different from contemporary humans.

Structuring the Unstructured: Databases for Paleolithic Art

Ewa Dutkiewicz

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Studies on Paleolithic art always face the problem of subjectivity. Artistic expressions are difficult to describe, are often multilayered or contradictory. They arise from a creative process, have no or not always clear practical functions and are ambiguous. But the situation is not hopeless. Works of art have parameters that can be determined and described using database technology. It is possible to differentiate between e.g. mobile and parietal art, determine the production technique or the used material. However, determining the topics and relationships between them remains the greatest difficulty. Even if figurative representations are supposed to be easy to understand, it does not necessarily mean that, for example, a horse only represents one horse. Depending on the cultural context, a lot of information can be conveyed using the representation of a horse. Although the taxonomic determination is clear in most cases, the meaning remains obscure. Does the representation of a mammoth in the form of an ivory statuette from the Aurignacian around 40,000 years ago have the same meaning as the 15,000 years old drawings on cave walls at Grotte de Rouffignac? Another point, especially when it comes to rock art, is to understand which pictures belong together. We know that the caves have been visited repeatedly and that figures have been added at different times. If we get a temporal resolution at all, what does that tell us about the scenes we supposedly recognize? Another difficulty lies in the so-called signs. These are usually geometric, abstract motifs that often accompany the figurative representations, but in many cases also stand alone. These signs are difficult to read because what is reflected in them is not immediately apparent. It could be, for example, as Henri Breuil and others have suggested, shortened representations of real objects. It could be fixed symbols, which, similar to characters, bear certain information. It could be notations and counts or just decorative elements.

In this poster, I would like to present some examples of current projects that have set themselves the task of structurally considering all aspects of Paleolithic art. Supra-regional and diachronic analyzes are intended to show connections and differences in the course of the Upper Paleolithic, which lasted several 10,000 years. On the one hand, the project "SignBase", which deals with geometric signs on mobile objects and on the other hand, a recently launched international project, which deals with animal representations in parietal and mobile art in Central and Western Europe.

METAhub Frankfurt – a database as link between museum cultures and performative art

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METAhub Frankfurt is based on a new form of cooperation between museum curators, documentaries and dramaturges on the one hand and coders and artists on the other. With "METAhub Frankfurt", the Jewish Museum and the Archaeological Museum Frankfurt are developing a digital application that brings together part of their collections, makes them available in narrative form and makes it possible to experience them in their former place as augmented reality. In an initial development phase, the early modern Judengasse, the Börneplatz synagogue and the early medieval imperial palace Franconofurd can be experienced digitally. In total, both museums have around 5,000 objects related to these locations. These include archaeological finds, ceremonial and everyday objects as well as numerous documents that can be used to reconstruct and tell stories. The Künstlerhaus Mousonturm and the NODE Forum are now inviting artists to perform performative interventions in the urban space with the digitized cultural goods, providing contact with coders who further develop the application and the reusable data, and as a digital partner brings its expertise in participatory development socio-political issues.

The Neotoma Paleoecology Database: Shared Standards, Community Curation, and Active Reanalysis of Paleo Data

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The Neotoma Paleoecology Database (www.neotomadb.org) is a community-curated data resource that supports interdisciplinary paleoenvironmental and global change research. Neotoma standardizes data structure and metadata across different data types, which facilitates common tool development and lowers data management costs. Neotoma makes paleoecological data openly available and offers a high-quality, curated resource.

Neotoma comprises virtual constituent databases for different types of data or for different regions. The constituent databases appoint data stewards, who are trained to validate and upload data and to help ensure high quality and completeness of data and metadata. Neotoma is living database that can be corrected or updated with additional data or metadata. Thus, two aspects of data curation are (1) initial validation and upload and (2) continued data maintenance. Other than correcting errors in original data submissions, examples of data updates include addition of new radiocarbon dates or new age models, which may be based on new radiocarbon dates, new radiocarbon calibration curves, or new age modeling techniques. An important example of new radiocarbon dates are the many new AMS dates that have been obtained on purified collagen from vertebrate specimens already in Neotoma. Various research projects have added many new age models developed with Bayesian methods or with other methods that provide estimates of the error in interpolated ages. Neotoma attempts to store sufficient metadata to replicate these age models.

Neotoma's distributed scientific governance model is flexible and scalable, with many open pathways for participation by new members, data contributors, stewards, and research communities. The Neotoma data model supports, or can be extended to support, any kind of paleoecological or paleoenvironmental data from sedimentary archives.

The Map Module for the ROAD Database

Christine Hertler

The Role of Culture in Early Expansions of Humans (ROCEEH), Heidelberg Academy of Sciences and Humanities, Senckenberganlage 25, 60325 Frankfurt am Main, Germany

ROAD makes use of a variety of tools to visualize data, among them the Map Module. The Map Module represents a handy way to display the geographical and temporal distribution of query results on a map. The Map Module offers a variety of services. First, it represents a simple way for anyone to check whether specific datasets are available in ROAD. In addition, registered users may apply the Map Module as a quick and simple way to display data on maps. The Map Module allows a user to select among a variety of maps, for instance displaying modern topography and climate as well as reconstructions of past climate and ecosystems – depending on specific research questions.

Finally, the Map Module serves as a link to other databases in order to search for additional data that are not stored in ROAD, thus avoiding redundancy in the efforts required in data collection. The Map Module provides a map interface in which query results from multiple databases can be joined and displayed. This can be achieved either graphically on the map or as a series of tables, which can be downloaded and subjected to further analysis, modeling or simulation. Applications in the Map Module are continuously updated and further developed. This poster introduces you to the main features of the Map Module and welcomes ideas for further development.

NeMo – An agent-based model for simulating Neanderthal mobility

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The Neanderthals existed for several thousand years until they mysteriously disappeared at around 30ka, leaving only rare traces modern human genes as well as in the archaeological and fossil record. The spatio-temporal patterning we may deduce from these remains are the accumulated result of small-scale decisions from Neanderthal groups. Therefore, understanding these spatio-temporal patterns would require to understand how the Neanderthals moved across the landscape. Moreover, a simulation approach would allow to apply an experimental context with which behavioral models could be tested.

For this purpose, we developed Neanderthal Mobility (“NeMo”), an agent-based model for simulating the movement of Neanderthal agents on a virtual landscape. The agent-based model incorporates GIS spatial data, locality data retrieved from the ROCEEH Out of Africa Database (ROAD) and behavioral models for hunter gatherer subsistence.

The environment of the agent-based model represents the geographic extent of France and adjacent regions which bear a lot of Neanderthal sites. The agents move, build residential- and logistical camps and forage for resources to fill up their energy storage. As outputs, we quantify the frequency, duration and distances of residential- and logistical camps in a given time period.

NeMo serves as a basis for the investigation of further possible analyses, e.g. to (i) compare the differences in mobility patterns between regions or clustering between regions. (ii) quantify the differences in mobility patterns between cold and warm phases or even (iii) incorporate additional features, such as differentiated subsistence strategies and raw material procurement.

NeMo exemplifies, how locality data retrieved from ROAD is used in conjunction with behavioral models to simulate the mobility of the Neanderthals. Furthermore, NeMo may act as a template how to simulate early hominin subsistence on the basis of topographic data.

ROAD Summary Data Sheet: A publication and data sharing tool

Zara Kanaeva ¹ and the ROCEEH Team ^{1,2}

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ROAD stands for the ROCEEH Out of Africa Database and contains archaeological and paleobiological data. It is a relational database with more than 50 tables. The information comes from publications written in English, German, French and several other languages. ROAD contains data for more than 1800 localities and 11,000 assemblages (as of June, 2020). The ROAD user interface has some visualization and querying tools, so a user who wishes to conduct for example quality control, can comfortably check selected parts of the database for the correctness of the data entered. Despite the convenience a user gains from these tools, he still needs to understand the structure of ROAD (tables and relations between the tables) in order to query all information for one selected locality. To gather all information for one locality stored in ROAD, a user would have to query about 50 tables.

To make the information stored in ROAD more easily accessible to scientists and the general public ROAD provides a tool for generating a datasheet summarizing each locality in the form of a PDF. This summary is a publication and can be used for scientific communication and education, data sharing and data control. The summary contains the essential part of the locality data including coordinates, layers, profiles, ages, assemblages and publication sources of the selected locality. The summary is published under a Creative Commons license (CC-BY-NC 4.0)

A Beginner's Guide to the ROCEEH Out of Africa Database

Andrew W. Kandel ¹ and the ROCEEH Team ^{1,2}

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In 2009, the ROCEEH team began integrating archaeological, paleoanthropological, paleontological and paleobotanical information into the ROCEEH Out of Africa Database (ROAD). As of June 2020, the team has compiled information on more than 1800 localities in Africa and Eurasia. ROAD now contains over 11,000 assemblages dated between about three million and 20,000 years before present. In this talk, I will present some of the achievements that ROAD has made over the last 12 years. In keeping with the framework of this conference, I refer each point to one of the five sessions of the conference, namely S1-Databases, S2-Methods, S3-Applications, S4-Products, and S5-Perspectives. In some cases, I draw attention to other members of the ROCEEH team who will present further details about our work during the conference.

One of ROAD's main functions is to preserve our human past as a resource for digital heritage in the future (Perspectives). It also serves as an educational tool in prehistory and the Quaternary sciences (Products). As part of our outreach, we sponsor workshops to acquaint users directly with the database and its many functions (Products). Furthermore, ROAD is a research tool with which a user can explore ideas and formulate hypotheses about human migration (Applications). Outputs from ROAD can be further tested using advanced techniques such as agent-based modeling (E. Hölzchen–Applications) and machine learning (C. Sommer–Methods).

While this talk provides a brief overview of the basic logical structure and semantics of ROAD (Databases), it will focus mainly on what the database can do. I will mention the benefits ROAD offers its users, such as querying data, visualizing results with the Map Module (C. Hertler–Applications), and conducting time series analysis with the Time Slice Tool (Methods). I will introduce the Summary Data Sheet, which provides an overview of each locality entered in ROAD (Z. Kanaeva–Applications) and show how data and maps from other large databases can be linked to ROAD. I will also discuss some ongoing research projects which collaborate using the data from ROAD (Applications). In sum, I hope to demonstrate how this database works as a powerful tool for researchers and the public alike.

Interdisciplinary challenges of the Cultural History of PaleoAsia project and its database development: Lessons learnt

Yasuhisa Kondo

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The Cultural History of PaleoAsia is a Japan-funded large-scale research project aimed at understanding the distinct patterns in the formation of modern human cultures across Asia. More than 50 researchers, including archaeologists, cultural anthropologists, mathematical biologists, and palaeoenvironmental scientists, have collaborated for this project. A team of the project is developing an archaeological site database to compile information on excavation, radiometric dating, lithic industry, and bibliographical reference. When this database was shared with natural scientists for joint research, the team found it difficult to share the key concepts such as culture, environment, and technology with them. Therefore, along with developing the database, the team is trying to span conceptual boundaries among the different domains involved. This invited talk shares the team's experience as lessons learnt and discusses how we can overcome such an interdisciplinary challenge.

To tackle this issue, the team applied lexical analysis, network graphs, and questionnaire surveys. First, a lexical analysis of the full text of the project's conference proceedings, annual reports, and website revealed that the term 'culture' was used in the context of materials (e.g. lithic culture, ceramic culture, etc.), geography (e.g. cultural zones), temporality (e.g. Aurignacian culture) and dynamics (e.g. cultural ecology). Second, the progress of interdisciplinary co-authorship was monitored through a network graph analysis of the conference proceedings; the number of co-authors was high in the archaeology groups and low in the cultural anthropology group. Third, a questionnaire survey revealed that cultural anthropologists prefer single authorship in comparison to other researchers. Regarding the fundamental concept of culture, 70% of the archaeologists chose 'behaviour'. Among cultural anthropologists and mathematical biologists, there was no poll for 'materials', while the numbers for 'behaviour' and 'information' were almost equal. Based on this evidence, the team is facilitating scholarly communication among researchers with different values and thoughts for better collaboration.

Spacialist – A Virtual Research Environment for the Spatial Humanities

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Many archaeological research projects generate data and tools that are abandoned after the project funding ends. Moreover, research data handling and the deployed tools are often highly specific for single projects. This practice leads to solutions that are incompatible with other tools, projects and infrastructures, and they often do not rely on accepted standards.

To close this gap, the project Spacialist was tasked to create a modular virtual research environment that offers an integrated, web-based user interface to record, browse, analyze, and visualize all spatial, graphical, textual and statistical data from archaeological or cultural heritage research projects. To address the highly heterogeneous requirements of such projects, Spacialist is developed as a software platform that is instantiated, customized and deployed for each research project. Spacialist uses project-specific controlled vocabularies based on the SKOS-XML standard, thus facilitating data analysis and interoperability with other projects and infrastructures.

The project is now beyond its development phase and is used by a number of projects in productive operation. In our presentation we will first present the functionalities and architecture of the software and then discuss in detail the experiences made so far. Special attention will be paid to the problem of sustainable further development and maintenance of Spacialist.

Matching datasets and palaeoenvironment to frame Human Palaeoecology in Europe around MIS 11

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The availability of trophic resources is one of the main factors that constraints the distribution and survival of any species, including hominins. Like any other organism, human beings aim always to adopt the most efficient feeding strategy for their given environmental conditions, under the limits of their own physiological constraints. Thus, in order to understand the survival strategies of ancient hunter-gatherer societies, we should look at the availability of trophic resources in their environment. We focus our attention on MIS 11, a key period for human biological and cultural evolution in Europe. In this period, the pre-existing populations progressively acquired the Neandertal anatomical characteristics, complex hunting activities were generalized, and the Prepared Core Technology (PCT) started to be widespread. Here we compiled information on the distribution of archaeological sites across Europe during MIS 11 from several datasets, including ROAD, and analysed the pattern of distributions of hominins in Western Europe with two proxies of resource availability. Net Primary Production (NPP) and Ungulate Carrying Capacity (CCU) for the MIS 11 were obtained from interpolated palaeoclimate maps as proxies for the abundance of plant and animal resources.

Is a decentralized, non-standardized approach to data sharing in archaeology good enough?

Shannon P. McPherron

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For decades there have been numerous efforts to design and build data standards and databases for the central storage, management and analysis of archaeological data. The success of these systems, as measured by participation and by research output, is varied. Mainly it seems that participation in these efforts is correlated with statutory requirements, and that in the absence of such enforcement mechanisms archaeologists continue to go their own way in terms of what they record and how (if) they share it. The good news is that in the meantime, significant technological advances have brought the ability of individual researchers to very effectively publish their data, and there appears to be an upcoming generation of archaeologists that are exploiting these new tools to good advantage. Here, I consider some of the benefits and drawbacks to this decentralized and non-standardized approach to data sharing, and I provide some practical examples. I conclude that in fact this approach may be better suited to much of research in archaeology.

A data-centric archaeological research methodology: opportunities and risks

Franco Niccolucci

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It is nowadays commonplace to consider the use and re-use of digital data as one of the pillars of archaeological research. The deposit of research data and the creation of aggregators such as ARIADNEplus in Europe and tDAR in the USA make available and searchable online very large catalogues of archaeological datasets – the former has now reached about two million items. Large thematic databases, also available on-line, as ROAD on human evolution with its more than 10,000 records, provide rich information on specific domains. Nevertheless, the information provided by these sources is still human-readable only, after a machine-made selection based on criteria defined by humans. The temptation of using more sophisticated technology is strong, but it must be cautiously analysed. Counting the data made available by such sources adds up to big numbers, but it is uncertain if they may be considered “Big Data”. Some argue that the blind application of Big Data techniques such as artificial intelligence or deep learning, so effective in many other fields, may lead to unpredictable and possibly misleading results when applied to archaeological data. On this regard there are enthusiastic but uncritical supporters as well as scholars expressing doubts that are not completely unjustified.

The lecture will discuss with examples why analysing the impact of digital data on the archaeological research methodology cannot be avoided or further postponed, and which are the concerns that at present still limit an effective use of advanced digital technology to automatically process, extract and combine them to produce new knowledge, mostly based on machine actions where humans intervene only to use the results. This will hopefully pave the way to a critical and informed use of technology which is the foundation for a data-centric archaeological research methodology.

Challenges of Archiving Complex Archaeological Datasets for Reuse: An Example from the American Southwest

Christopher Nicholson

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As datasets are “born digital” in both field and lab settings, archaeologists need to learn more about, and implement, plans for how their information will be 1) stored and cataloged in databases for analysis, 2) archived and preserved, and 3) reused by future generations. Creating data management plans at the onset of a project, which account for these issues, allows datasets to adhere to the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) in science. Abiding by these principles allows complex archaeological datasets to be properly archived and ultimately shared with a broader audience, especially when that information is deposited in a trusted repository. In this talk, I discuss these principles and provide an example of a complex dataset that meets these guidelines; the Mimbres Pottery Images Database. This dataset – archived in the repository tDAR (the Digital Archaeological Record) – contains images and data from over 9,000 Mimbres vessels from the American Southwest. A newly created tool in tDAR permits users to query the database and view a subset of the pottery images with associated metadata. The records returned in a given query is partially based on security clearance granted by the PI. Different levels of accessibility protect private collections and culturally sensitive information, while at the same time enables sharing the resource with a broader audience; thus, embodying the FAIR Principles.

Living in Sangiran

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Among many fossil-bearing localities in Java, Indonesia, Sangiran is the best-studied locality for hominid fossils. The stratigraphic sections in Sangiran hold a record of hominin occupation since at least 1.3 million years ago. The fossil and archaeological records in Sangiran includes hominid fossils, vertebrate and invertebrate fossils, pollen and other microfossils as well as artifacts throughout the stratigraphic section. Therefore, this site represents a unique window to study the early life of humans in Indonesia. As a follow up of fossil findings, paleoenvironmental aspects related to hominin occupation also have been long-studied in Sangiran. However, each study only focused on a certain proxies to reconstruct some environmental aspects in a limited area, covering hundreds of thousand years of interval. As a result, these studies did not give a comprehensive environmental background where hominin lived. Therefore, a reconstruction of a wider span of living area inhabited and exploited by a group (or more) of hominins in a scale of their lifetime is needed as a background to understand their behaviour and interaction through modeling and simulation.

In this study we focused to reconstruct the topography, hydrology, climatic/seasonal pattern and vegetation cover of Eastern part of Java, including Sangiran, at 1 million years ago. The result and implication will be discussed during the presentation. This reconstruction will later be used as a background to model and simulate hominin behaviour and interaction with their environment by using agent based modelling (ABM).

Paleo Core: A platform for data integration in paleoanthropology

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Paleoanthropology is transitioning from individual, project-focused initiatives to broader platform-focused initiatives that integrate data across multiple sources in order to address bigger-picture questions regarding human origins.

Initiated in 2012 with funding from the US National Science Foundation, Paleo Core hosts data from ten (and growing) active research projects with over 85,000 fossils, artifacts and geological samples and the ability to store geospatial locations for each item. Data from these collections is mapped to a standard data structure, which promotes data sharing, common best-practices for data acquisition and greater overall collaboration between formerly siloed research teams.

Paleo Core features a website and online platform for collecting, managing, and analyzing paleo-anthropological specimen data. The Paleo Core platform hosts tools to facilitate digital data collection in the field and to import these data into a central repository online. The online platform provides a web-based collaborative interface that allows research teams to manage biological, geological and archaeological collections effectively. It features a comprehensive conceptual model based on existing international data standards that foster data integration across projects. This integration is the keystone supporting linked-data and global search and query across research projects that choose to share and integrate their data.

Paleo Core is designed as a data management platform for researchers at the initial and intermediate stages of the data lifecycle, from data collection, analysis, publication up to accession in museum collection management systems. By providing the crucial infrastructure for digital data management at the acquisition and analysis phase, Paleo Core helps stem the tide of legacy analog data and promotes fully digital workflows from start to finish.

The specific problems of palaeontological databases and how NQMDB deals with them.

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The Neogene-Quaternary Mammals Database (NQMDB), hosted at CENIEH and accessible through ROAD, records information of mammalian species from the Neogene and Quaternary of Europe. As in many other databases focused on palaeontological data, lists of fossil taxa by site and stratigraphic unit constitute the core of the database. Moreover, to be useful for researchers, the occurrences of fossils should include also information on chronology. Thus, occurrence of a taxon at a place at a moment in time constitute the minimum information that should be recorded in a palaeontological database. However, out of this three variables, only the spatial location of the site where the fossils were found is known with certainty, and sometimes even this is not true. The two major problems that any palaeontological database should deal with are the uncertainty on the taxonomic identity of fossils and the uncertainty in their age. Given the fragmentary nature of the fossil record, it is frequent for different specialists to sustain different opinions about the taxonomic identity of a single fossil. Even worst, different taxonomists usually support alternative hypothesis about the phylogeny of a group, which produce different taxonomic classifications. The uncertainty about the age of a fossil is created by the existence of different dating methods, their accuracy and their reliability. Biostratigraphy is usually a highly reliable method, but it is very inaccurate. The accuracy of radiometric dating methods is variable, as well as their accuracy. The challenge for any palaeontological database is to record and organize all these uncertainties but, at the same time, be capable of providing data susceptible of being analyzed by researchers.

New perspectives for data exploration in ROAD

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Since 2009, the ROCEEH project has accumulated information on more than 20,000 assemblages in the ROCEEH Out of Africa Database (ROAD) from the fields of archaeology, paleoanthropology, paleontology, paleobotany as well as geographical information with landscape reconstructions and its diverse elements. Linked over space and time, these data allow a broader picture of the deep human past to be drawn. In parallel to the development of ROAD, AI analytical methods such as machine learning have become increasingly efficient and user-friendly in recent years. Supplementary to 'classic' analyses commonly used in the database (A. Kandel–Databases) and modelling approaches (C. Hertler–Applications), I will draw attention to further analytical methods, providing new opportunities to confirm existing hypotheses and discover patterns in the data that lead to the formulation of new hypotheses.

One example highlighted in this presentation investigates spatial human-environment interactions through the use of unsupervised classification to categorize archaeological sites by paleo-ecological conditions, and furthermore, predict potential habits through supervised classification. The derived suitability maps help to identify overlapping habitats, and thus potential migration corridors, as well as environmental barriers.

Another example focuses on methods to discover patterns of co-occurrence or obstruction of items in archaeological assemblages. Association rule mining is widely used in online marketing and applied to ROAD, offers the possibility to explore relations between e.g. the combination of lithic tools and site types on a quantitative basis. We conclude, how these methods benefit from the latest developments towards standardized data structures.

Combining Paleoenvironmental and Paleoanthropological Datasets to Understand Human Brain and Body Size Evolution

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Body and brain size are essential biological parameters of hominins. While recent research has clarified taxonomic and temporal trends within the human lineage, the causal mechanisms for these changes remain contentious, including environmental change, but also demographic, social, dietary and technological factors. Here we test the influence of environmental factors on the evolution of body and brain size in the genus *Homo* over the last 1.0 Ma by formalized hypotheses in a quantitative statistical framework. To this end, we for the first time combine a large fossil dataset (n=208) including spatial coordinates with a global climate model emulator that provides environmental variables for each space-time combination of individual fossils. Our results show different patterns of correspondence between modelled environmental variables and body and brain size evolution in *Homo*. Temperature predicted body size according to Bergmann's rule across all studied *Homo* taxa, likely a direct effect of climate on human physiology. On the other hand, net primary productivity and long-term variability in mean annual precipitation were good predictors of brain size in archaic but not modern humans. These environmental variables likely worked more indirectly in their effects, affecting cognitive abilities and extinction probabilities. While environmental challenges faced by hominins over their lifetime had some influence on body and brain size evolution in Middle Pleistocene *Homo*, Neanderthals and *Homo sapiens*, they explain only a part of the observed temporal patterns. Multiple interacting causal mechanisms at different time and on different taxa likely underlie the evolution of these key biological characteristics of *Homo* in the Pleistocene. Quantitative modelling with machine learning methods based on further interdisciplinary combination of large databases, for example from archaeology, will be key to further our understanding on brain and body size evolution within the genus *Homo*.

How well does the circumscription theory explain the formation of complex societies? Using agent-based models to evaluate archaeological theories against existing archaeological data

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How and why human societies began to form and sustain increasing levels of social complexity are heavily debated questions in archaeological research. Every region has unique trajectories of societal change but whether there are shared features between regions is a contentious issue. Similar factors relating to an increase social complexity are relatively easy to identify, such as the presence of warfare, organisational and agricultural intensification, charismatic leaders, or circumscribing barriers to population movement. It is much more difficult to objectively assess the influence of each of those factors and their general applicability across different societies and regions. The discussion on Carneiro's circumscription theory exemplifies this point. Multiple examples can be cited in either support or rejection of the importance of geographical, resource, or social barriers to population movement on the formation of social complexity. To resolve this debate, I developed agent-based models based on the assumptions of Carneiro's circumscription theory. These models allowed me to clarify the explicit and implicit assumptions of the theory and explore the range of conditions under which the theory is supported in abstract landscapes. To test the real-world applicability of the circumscription theory, I parameterised the models based on archaeological and environmental data from specific regions. The results from these experiments allow the precise quantification of the effects of circumscribing conditions on the formation of social complexity, and importantly, precisely highlight the gaps in archaeological research that need to be filled to firmly support or reject the circumscription theory. This research therefore shows the benefits of using agent-based models to move archaeological debates beyond stalemates, even when the data are limited.

PaleoMaps: Creating, collecting and compiling geospatial paleoenvironment data for culture-environment-interaction modeling applications

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In the frame of the Collaborative Research Centre 806 (CRC 806, www.sfb806.de), a German Research Foundation (DFG) funded interdisciplinary and inter-institutional research project, investigating human environment interaction (HEI) during the last 250.000 years, which was established in 2009 and is funded until 2021, considerable experience, competence and knowledge in integrating and managing data, information, and knowledge on HEI research was acquired and developed.

In this talk first the data management platform and repository CRC806-Database (crc806db.uni-koeln.de) will be presented, that was developed for the CRC 806 as a central data archive, and data publication platform. This will show, how the heterogeneous data that was produced and acquired by the project members, are organized in a web based platform.

This will be followed by the introduction of some example HEI modelling applications conducted within the CRC 806. These applications include for example Species Distribution Modelling (SDM), Least Cost Paths (LCP) and Site Catchment Analyses (SCA), Population Density Estimates, and more, which represents the state of the art in HEI modelling. One particular ingredient for almost any quantitative (and also for some qualitative) HEI modelling applications are computerized representations of well defined paleoenvironments.

Currently, this kind of data is published abundantly in the scientific record, but in very heterogeneous forms and formats. From implicit textual descriptions of huge regions to most detailed 3D models of small sites. From temporal categories of geological ages to exact and granular dates in time. By first investigating the state of the art in this field, data availability and accessibility, and looking at some exemplary geospatial paleoenvironment reconstructions in recent human-environment interaction modelling applications. The lack of a framework for sharing paleoenvironmental models or maps in the context of HEI modelling is addressed and discussed. This will be followed by a discussion and critique of state of the art approaches, leading to the definition and explanation of the PaleoMaps approach, that seeks to address the before identified shortcomings of existing approaches.

Prehistoric Population Dynamics — extended

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During the last two decades, methodologically interconnected projects at the University of Cologne investigated population dynamics of Prehistoric Societies. The so-called “Cologne Protocol” provided a consistent approach to estimate absolute population sizes as well as densities. Periods under consideration cover the Late Pleistocene (at Pan European scale, CRC 806 Project E1) and Holocene (for central Europe, LUCIFS). Altogether, estimates are currently available for 14 time-slices covering the last 40.000 years. Modelling of long-term population dynamics has been accomplished by interpolating between the obtained estimates using a logistic equation.

The poster will present the modelled long-term dynamics at the European scale and discuss future directions for extending its spatial and temporal framework. From our currently ongoing work, we present two potential pathways: Firstly, extending the spatial dimension, we draw from existing maps on cultural units and transfer estimates of the Cologne Protocol via regression analysis. Secondly, focusing on a temporal extension into earlier periods of human prehistory, we include georeferenced data from the “ROCEEH Out of Africa Database” (ROAD) on site occurrence and distribution. By applying the geostatistical upscaling procedure of the Cologne Protocol and data transfer from well-studied areas, our aim is to refine existing models on global prehistoric population dynamics.

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